

ARREST AND COMPARTMENTALISATION OF UNSTABLE COMPRESSIVE FAILURE IN CARBON-FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER LAMINATES USING A PLY-DISCONTINUITY FEATURE

Bruno P. Santos¹, Emile S. Greenhalgh² and Silvestre T. Pinho³

¹Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London
South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom

Email: b.santos22@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.nextcomp.ac.uk>

²Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London
South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom

Email: e.greenhalgh@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.nextcomp.ac.uk>

³Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London
South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom

Email: silvestre.pinho@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.nextcomp.ac.uk>

Keywords: Carbon fibre, Damage tolerance, Directional orientation, Fractography, Mechanical testing

ABSTRACT

Crack-arrest strategies are central to damage-tolerant structural design, particularly in large-scale components. By halting crack propagation and compartmentalising damage, such features prevent catastrophic failure, extend service life, and enable more flexible, cost-effective, and safer design approaches. This study developed a ply-discontinuity based feature to arrest unstable cracks in multidirectional Carbon-Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminates under compressive loading. The method targets the arrest of unstable kink-band propagation by replacing 0° plies with off-axis ones. This reconfiguration promotes fracture energy reflection and dissipation, while altering failure mechanisms, enabling the laminate to arrest high-velocity cracks (~1 km/s) and improve ultimate failure strain. Validation was performed using IM7/8552 CFRP elements incorporating off-axis ply regions with additional local reinforcement to preserve longitudinal stiffness. Two different crack-arrest element configurations were tested. These configurations differed from one another by the off-axis ply orientations used to replace 0° plies ($\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$). Mechanical performance was monitored via strain gauges and digital image correlation. Post-failure analysis employed C-scans, radiography imaging, and scanning electron microscopy to characterise damage evolution and arrest mechanisms. Both lay-up configurations successfully arrested crack propagation and significantly increased strain capacity. Enhancements in ultimate failure strain reached up to 38% for $\pm 30^\circ$ elements and up to 100% for $\pm 45^\circ$ elements. Repeated tests confirmed result reproducibility. These findings demonstrate the potential of ply-discontinuity features for improving damage tolerance in composite structures and provide insight into their underlying failure-arrest mechanisms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Compressive performance, particularly in the presence of in-service damage, remains a key limitation in composite structural design. Compressive strength of Fibre-Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) is significantly inferior to their tensile performance, generally corresponding to 60-70% of latter [1]. Factors such as high sensitivity to manufacture defects and a complex combination of failure modes are the main responsible for this discrepancy [2-3]. Additionally, if compressive failure initiates in a component, there are no means to arrest such fracture. As a result, composite structures are typically designed under a 'no-damage-growth' philosophy. Transitioning to a 'damage-growth tolerance'

approach, where controlled crack propagation is permissible, would unlock the full structural potential of composites.

Central to this philosophy are crack-arrest strategies, which aim to contain unstable failure, compartmentalise damage and extend service life. Such features are well-established in other engineering fields. In compressed-gas transmission pipelines, ribs are used to contain long tensile cracks in metallic pipes [4,5]. Similarly, in aircraft fuselages tear straps are used to stop tear propagation in the composite skin [6]. Nevertheless, little to no research has addressed compressive crack-arrest in fibrous composite laminates.

By developing an unstable crack-arrest feature for CFRP compression, this research aspires to pave the way to fail-safe design in large composite structures. Such feature enables the design of components that remain operational following initial unstable fracture. Thus, it enhances safety and allows lighter and more permissible structural designs. These benefits are particularly critical in applications where failure has life-threatening consequences, such as in aircraft wing roots. Figure 1 exemplifies how such a feature would be able to avoid structural collapse in a damaged wing root.

Figure 1: Representation of compressive-crack compartmentalisation on a damaged aeroplane wing.

(a) Crack propagation from the damaged region without crack arrest mechanisms, unrestrictedly expanding across the wing's chord and causing catastrophic failure. (b) Failure compartmentalisation by periodic crack-arrest bands, allowing the wing to remain in service.

2 FEATURE CONCEPT

Unstable compressive crack propagation in CFRPs can reach speeds approaching 1 km/s [7]. This rapid growth is driven by the propagation of out-of-plane kink-bands, which then facilitate the formation of secondary fracture types [8]. Due to the high energy involved, arresting crack growth requires mechanisms that dissipate or deflect associated fracture energy. Thus, a ply-discontinuity-based feature was developed. This feature exploits the fact that kink-bands typically occurs in 0° plies and propagate perpendicular to the loading direction. Thus, by locally replacing these plies with off-axis ones, it may be possible to divert or even arrest an unstable compressive fracture. Additionally, lay-ups dominated by 0° plies ("hard lay-ups") show lower translaminar toughness than off-axis-only ("soft lay-ups") configurations. Hence, introducing ply discontinuities creates regions of higher toughness, enhancing crack containment and resistance to propagation.

Importantly, the developed feature uses only existing, certified aerospace materials. This simplifies certification and facilitates integration into current aerospace structures. Furthermore, using a single composite type also eases recycling and end-of-life material handling.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

To validate this concept, test elements were designed and manufactured using IM7/8552 carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy. Additional reinforcement layers were introduced in soft lay-up regions, to maintain longitudinal stiffness across the width of the panel. A U-notch (10 mm length and 5 mm diameter) was designed to induce unstable failure around $-3100 \mu\epsilon$. This value was chosen for being slightly above the $-2500 \mu\epsilon$ design limit load typically used in aerospace industry [9]. Sandwich configuration, with aluminium honeycomb core and CFRP skins, was employed to prevent global buckling during testing (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Compression test element geometry. Being the interest region, the frontal skin is divided in soft and hard lay-ups, and equipped with a notch to induce failure initiation. The rear skin is composed only by the hard lay-up and does not possess a notch.

The 200×200 mm element gauge area represents only a small fraction of a full-scale structure's overall dimensions. Therefore, even the loss of the entire 200mm section would not represent a significant reduction in the complete structure's load-bearing capacity. Thus, the most reliable indicator of a given element's performance is not their load capacity but their strain tolerance. This tolerance represents the structure's capability of being deformed before collapsing.

To control test variables, specific constraints were applied during the definition of the skins' lay-ups. Since the hard lay-up is multidirectional, while 0° layers were replaced by off-axis ones, the remaining plies were maintained continuous to conserve element integrity. Both lay-ups were designed as symmetrical, eliminating compression-bending coupling effects. Finally, additional plies were added to the soft lay-up to match stiffness across the element width. To minimise undesired stress concentration, the lay-up transition was implemented gradually, forming a 'ramp' profile. The front skin, identified as the primary surface of interest, was the only one containing the arrest feature.

Two different lay-up configurations were tested, differentiated by distinct off-axis ply angles ($\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$) replacing the 0° oriented plies. For each configuration two identical Crack-Arrest (CA) elements were tested, as well as a suitable baseline. This sought to ensure the reproducibility of the crack-arrest behaviour. The baselines consisted in panels without arrest feature, in which the entirety of the frontal skin was composed by the hard lay-up.

Lower longitudinal stiffness of 45° plies, when compared to 30° ones, implicated in a higher number of additional soft lay-up plies. The $\pm 30^\circ$ feature configuration had 19 and 33 plies in its hard and soft regions, respectively. Meanwhile, panels with the $\pm 45^\circ$ feature configuration had 19 and 55 plies in their hard and soft lay-ups.

The elements were tested in a 250-tonne screw-driven compression test machine under displacement control. Mechanical behaviour during tests was assessed using strain gauges and digital

image correlation, while post-failure analysis was performed through C-scans, radiography imaging, and optical and scanning electron microscopy to better understand failure initiation and arrest mechanisms.

4 RESULTS

As expected, both baseline elements suffered abrupt failures that propagated across the entire width of their notched skins. These fractures lead to the collapse of the baseline elements, with almost complete loss of load-bearing capability. The failure of the crack-arrest elements, however, was successfully stopped upon reaching the beginning of the arrest region. Following this initial failure, additional strain was endured by the elements, progressively causing smaller failure steps. Ultimate failure was achieved when the crack front reached the opposite end of the frontal skin width. Figure 3 represents the test behaviour of both baseline elements, as well as one element of each crack-arrest feature configuration. The remaining elements showed similar results to those represented, attesting to the reproducibility of these results.

Figure 3: Evolution of applied strain for both crack-arrest configurations, as well as their respective baselines. Both configurations were successful in stopping failure propagation and increasing ultimate failure strain. Notably, the 45° configuration was able to double the strain to failure of its baseline.

It is possible to observe that both feature configurations showed elastic behaviour compatible with their respective baselines before initial failure. Additionally, the baselines failed near -3100 µε strain, as per the notch design.

For the feature lay-up using $\pm 30^\circ$ off-axis plies, baseline failure happened at -3070 µε, while that of the CA element started at -2980 µε. The chart still portrays its subsequent growth steps, up to the ultimate failure at -4230 µε. This represents a 38% increase in ultimate failure strain. Repeating the test with an identical element, similar behaviour was observed, resulting in an ultimate failure strain increase of 33%. It is notable that, although possessing the same stiffness as the baseline, the CA elements presented ultimate strains to failure one third higher than it.

Meanwhile, for the feature lay-up using $\pm 45^\circ$ off-axis plies, the baseline panel failed at -3230 µε. CA failure started at -3800 µε, being subsequently arrested, and final panel collapse happened at -6460 µε. This constitutes a 100% increase in ultimate failure strain, with results from a repeat test showing an 85% strain increase. Hence, this configuration is capable of nearly doubling its baseline performance.

Radiographies and C-scans were employed to visualise subsurface damage in each element. The radiography images presented in Fig. 4 allow visualisation of the main failure path and secondary fractures for representative elements.

Figure 4: Radiographies of fracture regions for the different test elements, portraying the change in failure path caused by ply-discontinuity. Differences in delamination area surrounding fracture are also visible.

Both baselines behaved in a similar manner, with fracture showing a tendency of propagating perpendicular to loading direction. The same behaviour appears in the hard lay-up regions of the CA elements. However, the soft lay-up regions exhibit a modified failure path, with fracture propagating in oblique directions. Moreover, in the $\pm 45^\circ$ CA element, fracture propagation was split into two main failure paths after the initial arrest. Significantly higher amounts of delamination are also observable in the soft lay-ups, when compared to their hard counterparts.

5 DISCUSSION

Both versions of the developed feature were successful in compartmentalising unstable failure growth. However, the increase in ultimate failure strain provided by the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies was significantly higher than that of the $\pm 30^\circ$ plies. This configuration nearly doubled strain tolerance, even withstanding higher loads than its baseline despite significant panel section loss.

It is important to consider, however, the additional weight penalty inherent to this configuration. The usage of a ply direction with lower longitudinal stiffness results in a higher thickness in the soft lay-up section. Nevertheless, in real work conditions such penalty could be mitigated by adjusting the frequency and width of periodic crack-arrest bands. Moreover, this concept introduces the possibility of fail-safe design, creating thinner panels and achieving weight reduction for the overall structure.

Analysing the fracture properties in Fig. 4, a better understanding of the mechanisms responsible for the feature's success becomes possible. It is notable that, as seen in the baseline, initial fracture in the CA elements grew perpendicular to load application direction. Similar fracture morphology was also observed between these failures, consistent with the baseline's suitability as comparison. Nevertheless, following the initial arrest, the subsequent failure in the CA elements presented significant changes in both growth direction and fracture morphology. These behavioural changes hint as to the effects of the of ply replacement in obstructing the kink-band propagation.

The concepts key component is the removal of fibres that would enable kink-band to propagate in its preferential growth direction. Upon reaching a geometric discontinuity in lay-up, a fraction of the dynamic fracture energy is reflected, reducing its momentum. Beyond that, in the absence of 0° plies to allow perpendicular growth, fracture is forced to seek alternative routes. This increases the length of the failure path, resulting in higher energy dispersion and posing an obstacle to failure growth.

Together with the more tortuous failure path caused by crack deflection, the increase in secondary damage surfaces contributes to energy dissipation. These factors also hint to the reasons behind the higher performance of the $\pm 45^\circ$ feature configuration. By further redirecting the fracture's path and successfully splitting its growth into two main fronts, this lay-up potentializes energy dissipation. Similarly, this behaviour results in a significantly higher amount of secondary fracture surfaces, hampering crack growth.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A crack-arrest concept for CFRPs under compression was developed and experimentally validated. The feature successfully arrested unstable kink-band propagation, significantly delaying ultimate failure and enhancing the strain tolerance of the tested elements. Two configurations of the feature were tested, using off-axis angles of $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$. Their performances were compared to suitable baselines and to one another.

The feature operates by locally introducing fibre orientation discontinuities, which deflect the crack and create longer, more tortuous failure paths. This results in increased kink-band energy dissipation. Additionally, the soft lay-up experiences more secondary damage, aiding energy dissipation and enhancing crack arrest.

The $\pm 30^\circ$ feature demonstrated a one-third increase in ultimate failure strain, relative to its baseline. Meanwhile, the $\pm 45^\circ$ feature was able to nearly double its baseline's strain tolerance. When compared to one another, the $\pm 45^\circ$ feature was evaluated as the most promising, displaying larger amounts of secondary fracture and longer failure paths. Therefore, despite possessing a larger weight penalty, its significant increase in ultimate strain represents a promising route for fail-safe design.

Future work will focus on reducing the weight penalty associated to the crack-arrest feature. For that purpose, the minimum arrest band width necessary to stop failure propagation will be defined.

Additionally, a study of weight penalty reduction by reinserting stiffer plies into the soft lay-up will be performed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors kindly acknowledge the funding for this research provided by UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) programme Grant EP/T011653/1, Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites (NextCOMP): a Full-Scale Redesign for Compression a collaboration between Imperial College London and the University of Bristol. For the purpose of open access, the authors have applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to any author accepted manuscript version arising.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Sun et al. "Experimental and computational analysis of failure mechanisms in unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polymer laminates under longitudinal compression loading". In: *Composite Structures* 203 (2018), pp. 335–348 (see p. 1).
- [2] S. Nunna, A.R. Ravindran, J. Mroszczok, C. Creighton and R.J. Varley. A review of the structural factors which control compression in carbon fibres and their composites, *Composite Structures*, 303, p.116293, 2023.
- [3] C.V. Opelt, G.M. Cândido and M.C. Rezende. Compressive failure of fiber reinforced polymer composites – A fractographic study of the compression failure modes, *Materials Today Communications*, 15, pp.218-227, 2018.
- [4] B.M. Albaghdadi and A.O. Cherniavsky. Possibility of using ribs to protect pipelines from the long crack propagation, *Bulletin of the South Ural State University. Ser. Mechanical Engineering Industry*, 16(3), pp.15-20, 2016.
- [5] X.K. Zhu. State-of-the-art review of fracture control technology for modern and vintage gas transmission pipelines, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 148, pp.260-280, 2015.
- [6] A. Velicki and D.C. Jegley. PRSEUS structural concept development, In 52nd Aerospace Sciences Meeting, p. 0259, 2014.
- [7] J. Ankersen et al. Dynamic fracture in CFRP panels under compressive loading. Proceedings of the 15th European Conference on Composite Materials. 2012.
- [8] E.S. Greenhalgh. Failure analysis and fractography of polymer composites. Elsevier, pp.117-126, 2009.
- [9] E.S. Greenhalgh. Technical Evaluation of DAMOCLES; Damage Management of Composite Structures for Cost-Effective Life-Extensive Service, Technical Report QinetiQ/FST/TR023421, 2002.